

Designing an AI Framework to Predict Real-Time Online Learning Comprehension Among Undergraduates

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Abstract

Effective real-time procedures to evaluate student understanding are more important now than ever before due to the growing popularity of online learning in higher education, especially in the post-pandemic period. Teachers can see non-verbal clues like facial expressions and behavioral reactions in traditional classroom settings, which are mostly missing in virtual ones. This study suggests creating a multimodal Artificial Intelligence (AI) framework that combines response accuracy and facial expression analysis to forecast undergraduate students' real-time understanding. Based on learning analytics and affective computing, the study uses a mixed-methods approach, collecting and analyzing qualitative and quantitative data simultaneously using a convergent parallel architecture. Quantitative data were acquired from 384 lecturers through structured questionnaires and 147 undergraduate students through an online learning platform designed expressly for this project. Semi-structured interviews with 15 lecturers were conducted to explore pedagogical insights and ethical considerations.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Comprehension Prediction, Facial Landmark Analysis, Multimodal Learning Analytics, Online Education.*